

**COMPARATIVE STUDY OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS WITH THE
SOMATIC COMPONENT IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK
(IN THE EXAMPLE OF THE CONCEPT OF LOVE)**

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ABSTRACT

The article represents about phraseologisms describing the concept of “love” in English and Uzbek languages, including structural-semantic aspects of phrases with somatism component, are compared. Researches and opinions of world linguists on this issue have been collected. Examples are analyzed in two languages and their isomorphic and allomorphic aspects are contrasted. In general, the essence of the concept of “love” in the culture of the speakers of the language, its application, and how its verbalization is important in the language are highlighted.

KEYWORDS: concept, somatism, somatic phraseological units, component, lexeme, implementation, symbol, culture, verbalization, classification.

INTRODUCTION

"Love" is the main concept of culture, which determines the values, and orientations of the society and the related language culture. The concept of "love" cannot be analyzed cognitively without phraseological units, which are also involved in the verbalization of the concept. The reason is that phraseologisms "in their semantics reflect the long process of cultural development of people, record cultural attitudes, stereotypes, standards and archetypes and transfer them from generation to generation" [1, 132].

Phraseological units directly reflect the connection between language and culture. Everything describing people's lifestyle, national psychology and customs, traditions, and mentality is focused on phraseological units. That is why the phraseology of any language has a national character, and its study helps to analyze the history and character of the nation in depth. It is known that phraseological units differ from words in their stylistic value, expressiveness and national-cultural specificity. The importance and role of phraseological units require the study of phraseological units as a type of verbalization of the concept of "love".

MAIN PART

In phraseology, a special group of somatic phraseological units is distinguished. "The component part of these phraseological units includes words denoting this or that part of the body - somatisms" [3, 107]. Somatism is derived from the Greek word "soma" which means "body". Somatism, a somatic phraseological unit or phraseological unit with a somatic component means gestures, facial expressions and expressions related to the psychosomatics of the human body [2, 570].

The term "somatic" was introduced into linguistics by F. Vakk when he analyzed Estonian phraseological units. The study of somatic phraseology in world linguistics began in the second half of the 20th century. F. Vakk, G.A. Bagautdinova, S.G. Alekseeva, R.M. Weintraub, R. Yu. Mugu, Ye.V. Nikolina, O.A. Kononova, V.P. Shubina, M.N. Azimova, T.N. Chaiko, T.N. The works of Fedulenkova and others are devoted to the study of somatic phraseology. The study of somatic phraseologisms in Uzbek linguistics was carried out by such scientists as Ya. Pinkhasov, Sh. Rakhmatullaev, A. Hojiev, B. Yoldoshev, A. Mamatov, A. Isaev, Sh. Abdullaev, Sh. Usmonova [5, 181].

The leading linguist scientist in Uzbek linguistics - phraseologist Sh. Rahmatullaev divides phraseological units in terms of semantic types into a) nominative (nominative) phraseological units, and b) expressive (communicative) phraseological units. Based on this classification, there is every reason to divide phraseologisms promoting the concept of "love" into the following types:

Nominative phraseological units: **Uzb.** ko`ngli qattiq, ko`ngli tosh, yuragi tosh, bag`ri tosh, ko`z qorachig`i, ko`zining oq-u qorasi, ko`ngil bo`lmoq, ko`ngil bog`lamoq, yuragiga qo'l solmoq/ko`ngliga qo'l solmoq ,yulduzi yulduziga to'g'ri keldi, es-hushini olib qo'ymoq. **Eng:** apple of my eye , be an item, blind date, double dating, drive someone crazy, get hitched, have the hots for, head over heels, leave at the altar, love is blind, to fancy someone, walk out on someone, lovey-dovey, no love lost, a love nest, to have eyes only for someone, cupboard love, loveseat etc.

Communicative phraseological units: **Uzb.** Birov parini sevibdi, Birov — qurbaqani; Vafoli qul — jafoli qul; Gul — bahona, diydor — g`animat; Gul — hayot bezagi, Sevgi — inson bezagi; Muhabbat yosh tanlamas; Ishq boshqa, havas boshqa; Ishq — muqaddas o`t; **Eng:** The way to a man's heart is through his stomach; There is no difference between a wise man and a fool when they fall in love; Absence makes the heart grow fonder; Two shorten the road; Opposites attract; Beauty is in the eye of the beholder; Love yourself or no one else will.

<p>Ishqi tushdi/Mehri tushdi- yoqtirib qoldi. “Adolatga ko`zi tushgan,ishi tushgan, ishqi tushgan yigitlarning hammasi ana shunday xayolning asiriga aylanardi.”[I.Rahim,Chin muhabbat]</p>	<p>To fall for someone- to fall in love `He falls for a girl who is like a film-star`</p>
<p>Jigaridan/yuragidan urmoq- o`ziga shaydo qilib olmoq. “ Qo`yingki do`ndiqcha jigardan urib qoldi. Nima qilsam yoqarkanman deb o`lib bo`laman”.[S.Anorboyev. Oqsoy]</p>	<p>One`s heart skips/ misses a beat- feel so excited that heart beats faster. `Her heart skipped a beat as a lean figure in a business suit entered the room.</p>

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The most quantitatively expressed somatic phraseological units are phraseological units that express the emotional state of love. Describing this emotional state in the language picture of the world of speakers of English, Uzbek and other languages is carried out with the help of traditional symbols through the language of physiological

changes that occur with the heart. In the linguistic picture of the world of these peoples, the heart is the centre of affection, love, emotions, and predictions: kind / tender heart — mehribon yurak, rahmdil - доброе сердце; a heart of gold — oltin yurak va boshqalar.

The state of love in the landscape of the world of these peoples is perceived as the disintegration, destruction, and loss of the heart, and soul. Phraseological units are used to describe this state of depression: the components dili vayron bo'lmoq, yuragi parchalanmoq - to lose heart (courage), parchalamoq, vayron bo'lmoq reflect the verb "to lose".

The expression of this situation in the English language is also related to the concept of "enter". Compare: gain (win) smb.'s heart (the heart of smb.) - yurakka kirmoq; kimningdur yuragiga (birovning qalbiga) kirmoq.

In the linguistic landscape of the world, involuntarily, coercion prevails in the description of love, which is clearly manifested in the semantics of phraseological units describing the ways to achieve love. There are a number of phraseological units in comparable languages, which are expressed in phraseological units in the linguistic landscape: kimningdir yuragini bo'ysundirmoq, kimningdir qalbini qozonmoq, biror kimsaning yuragini zabt etmoq, birovning muhabbatiga erishish - **gain somebody's heart** ; conquer (gain, win) the heart of smb. (smb.'s heart) [5,182].

In English linguistics, there are feelings of love related to the animal world, in which we can observe a direct image of an animal, for example: 'puppy love, calf love, sheep's eyes, here is 'puppy' – kuchukcha, 'calf' – buzoq, 'a sheep' is qo'y . They form figurative expressions: puppy love - bolalar sevgisi, calf love - bolalar sevgisi, ya'ni ular "birinchi sevgi" deb ataladigan narsani anglatadi, sheep's eyes' esa - qo'y ko'zlari, the image of a sheep is not just random, it is known from the history of England that this domestic animal is treated with respect. In the Uzbek language, there is no such analogy for animals.

In Uzbek, there are expressions used with the word “ko‘z” - "eye", which are used very often among the people: ko‘ziga o‘tday ko‘rinmoq, ko‘zining oqu qorasi, ko‘z qorachig‘i, ko‘zining qorachig‘i, ko‘z ochib ko‘rgan. In addition, there are the

noun phrases used with the component ko'z such as ko'z qorachig'i, ko'z(i)ning qorachig'i and the adverb idiomatic phraseology, i.e. ko'z ochib ko'rgan, ko'z qorachig'idek, ko'z qorasidek.

Phraseological units with the lexeme "head" are the second most frequently used in English: **to lose one's head about smb, be/fallhead over heels in love** (to love or suddenly start to love someone very much).

Having studied the phraseological units with the "head- бош" component in Sh.Rahmatullaev's "Phraseological Dictionary of the Uzbek Language", we witnessed that they are often used in the meaning of marriage: **бошларини қовуштирмак, бошларини бириктирмак, бошларини қўшмак, бир бошни икки қилмак, бир ёстикка бош қўймак** [4; P.39-55]. The use of other phraseological units **бошини айлантормак** or **бош-қўзини айлантормак** in the sense of charming someone, **бошига кўтармак** in the sense of showing affection to someone, showing high respect to someone can be the basis for inclusion in the group of phraseology with the concept of love [4; P.45-46].

In English, the lexeme "heart" is used in different meanings, and one of its meanings is love: lose one's heart – севиб қолмак, steal somebody's heart – бировнинг кўнглини олмак, affair of the heart – ишқий саргузаштлар, somebody's heart rules their head- ақлини қалби бошқариши, win somebody's heart – севгисини қозонмак, a broken heart – севгидан синган қалб. In the paradigm of phrases with a heart-юрак component, most of the verb phrases are formed: юрагидан урмак ,юрагига қўл солмак , юрагини очмак. In this case, the heart somatism in the noun group accepts the additions of the agreement of departure, arrival and departure and serves to form phrases. The word "ўт-fire" in the phrase Юрагида ўт ёнмак is equivalent to a flame in a person's psyche, heart [6].

CONCLUSION

Thus, phraseological units with somatism among these peoples are primarily associated with the expression of the emotional state of love. In general, the general conceptual properties of a given emotional state find the same implementation in the linguistic picture of the world of these peoples. The differences come down to the

productivity of phrase formation with somatism "heart" in the compared languages, to a greater or lesser extent, the implementation of one or another differential semantic feature. On the other hand, the concept of "love" in the compared languages is closely related to such concepts as jealousy, passion and excitement, in the language implementation of which this somatism is also actively used. Comparative study of the phraseology of different languages serves to deepen the understanding of the structure of both languages, to enrich knowledge about the verbs, culture, literature, history, and customs of the people who own these languages. In Uzbek and English phraseology, units related to somatisms occupy a significant place, and this is explained by the active participation of human body parts in the process of daily activities and mental experiences.

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